

Selection of sustainable development indicators of agro-food chain in Valle del Cauca

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The Project, "Integral program of knowledge transfer for sustainable development of the food chain in Valle del Cauca region", performed by Universidad del Valle (Colombia) and Universidad de Almería (Spain) during 2012 and 2013. This sustainable development must meet requirements in topics such environmental and economic needs of the actual and future communities. Its objective was to contribute to sustainable development in the agricultural production.

Experts in different areas of knowledge were called. With people accepted the invitation a team was formed. First task was to select an agro-food chain and define the concept of sustainability. Papaya (*Carica papaya*) food chain was selected to the experimental part. The papaya food chain's actors were identified. Information was requested to papaya growers. Information was requested to papaya growers through personal surveys. Information about papaya production was collected (agronomical, environmental and occupational health). This information helped the team will select the sustainability indicators. A database of Sustainability Indicators among those chosen was created and analyzed. The team selected three: **Good Agricultural Practices** – GAP (agricultural and social item), are the most important indicator because include environmental, economic and social sustainability for on-farm processes, and its impact in safe and quality food and non-food agricultural products. **Virtual Water Flow** (environmental item), estimates the conceptual volume of water needed to produce a food and non-food agricultural products. **Environmental Impact Quotient**, EIQ (environmental economic and social item), is one of the more used indicators because is a composite environmental impact assessment system, that permits the integration into one value of several important environmental and human health impacts. Finally the web page was created and indicator was programmed so that farmers can enter their data and obtain the value of the indicators.

We conclude the proposed method for assessing agricultural sustainability through indicators has practical value and applicability. The application of the selected indicators help farmers to take decisions with respect to the amount, intervals of application, and changing of the pesticides and other products in agro-food chain cropping fields.

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